

Evaluating Facebook scales: A systematic review of the psychological assessment tools

Francesca BRUNO¹, Aurora MAUTONE², Driss AIT ALI³, Abdelfattah FASSIMA⁴, Hicham KHABBACHE⁵, Amelia RIZZO^{6*}

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¹Department of Cognitive Sciences, Pedagogical Psychological and Cultural Studies, University of Messina, Messina, Italy. E-mail: francescabruno@blu.it ORCID: 0009-0007-1842-2470

²Department of Clinical and Experimental Medicine, Messina, Italy. E-mail: aurora.mautone.25@gmail.com ORCID: 0009-0006-6470-7381

³Psychology Department, Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University, Fes, Morocco. E-mail: Driss.aitali@usmba ORCID: 0000-00015043-9677

⁴Psychology Department, Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University, Fes, Morocco. E-mail: abdefattah.fassima@usmba.ac.ma ORCID: 0009-0005-9968-9315

⁵Lifelong Learning Observatory (UNESCO, USMBA), Department of Psychology, Faculty of Lifelong Learning Observatory (UNESCO, USMBA), Department of Psychology, Faculty of Arts and Human Science Sciences Saïss, Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University, Fes, Morocco. E-mail: hicham.khabbache@usmba.ac.ma ORCID: 0000-0001-9587-2829

⁶Department of Clinical and Experimental Medicine and Department of Cognitive Sciences, Pedagogical Psychological and Cultural Studies, University of Messina, Messina, Italy. E-mail: amrizzo@unime.it ORCID: 0000-0002-6229-6463

* Correspondence

Abstract

Introduction: Research on Facebook has predominantly focused on quantitative aspects such as time spent online, number of friends, frequency of posts, status updates, and friends' posts. This study aims to review the existing questionnaires developed to measure Facebook's psychological aspects, particularly motivations and gratifications, to provide valid tools for researchers in the field.

Methods: A systematic literature review was conducted, limited to articles published in English between 2004, when Facebook was launched, and 2024. The research focused on non-clinical samples, particularly university students, and studies measuring Facebook psychological attitudes relevant to personality trait assessment.

Results: Twenty-four articles met the inclusion criteria and were analyzed based on methodological characteristics, including the nationality (language) of the studies, sample features, structure of the instruments, correlated personality measures, and results of validity and reliability analyses.

Discussion: The analysis reveals a significant variability in the psychometric properties of the reviewed instruments. While some questionnaires demonstrate strong validity and reliability,

others require further refinement and validation. The study underscores the importance of ongoing efforts to enhance the psychometric quality of these tools to ensure accurate measurement of the psychological impacts of Facebook use. The review serves as a critical resource for researchers, guiding the selection of the most appropriate and robust scales for future studies in social media psychology.

Take-home message: This review systematically evaluated and compared existing questionnaires measuring the psychological aspects of Facebook use, highlighting the need for further validation and refinement of many of these tools to ensure their effectiveness in research.

Keywords: Facebook uses; Facebook questionnaire; psychological assessment; social networking sites; measurement.

INTRODUCTION

Studies on social networks, and Facebook in particular, are common. Researchers have paid much more attention to studying the different aspects related to Facebook users. Research has been conducted to understand the relationship between Facebook users, political decisions, social behaviors, tastes, preferences, economic behavior, and even personality traits [1,2].

This last point is of great interest to psychology, especially in the field of "psycho-technologies" [3], which examines the impact of new technologies on the mind. This includes implications for identity, relationships, psychopathology, cognitive functions such as memory and attention, and individual aspects like feelings of loneliness versus group belonging in virtual environments.

To study these relationships in a quantifiable and measurable way, many instruments have been developed over time to investigate the use of Facebook. In this article, we will not address the sociological, political, or economic aspects but refer exclusively to the psychological dimensions.

In particular, we focused on a topic of interest to clinical psychology and psychiatry: the relationship between attitudes, motivations, and personality traits regarding Facebook use.

The examination of the literature has indeed highlighted that Facebook usage correlates with aspects relevant to extroversion, increased social relations, maintenance of stable ties, expansion of superficial bonds, trust, and Self-satisfaction [4-7]. On the one hand, using social networks would support developing and maintaining social relations, favoring extroversion and satisfaction. On the other hand, the relationship between these variables is correlational; extroversion and self-esteem may act as precursors of pro-social use mediated by Facebook.

Much of the literature shows that Facebook use is related to fewer offline friendships and increased feelings of loneliness, shyness, alienation, and social introversion [8-10]. The authors suggest that extensive use of Facebook as a substitute for face-to-face interactions may exacerbate feelings of social exclusion and non-belonging, leading to further withdrawal. This creates a vicious circle where increased online time perpetuates emotional and social isolation.

But how is it possible that using the same tool is related to traits with opposite polarities? These controversial results suggest that there may be a measurement bias. The International Test Commission (ITC) guidelines for good test use and encouraging best assessment practices recommend advanced quality control.

Moreover, researchers often develop new tools for studying Facebook use instead of using those already existing in the literature. While this customization helps researchers capture specific aspects they are interested in, it complicates the process of making fair

comparisons across different studies and findings [11]. In addition, selecting the appropriate instrument and comparing the features of various questionnaires can be time-consuming during the research planning phase [12].

Furthermore, not all tools are methodologically reliable unless accompanied by validity analyses, such as assessments of factorial structure, principal components, sensitivity, and reliability, often expressed using Cronbach's alpha [12].

With this in mind, the present systematic review aims to identify a list of the available instruments developed for assessing Facebook uses and gratifications and provide a comprehensive psychometric review of each item. Researchers interested in improving measurement in Facebook psychological research can use this study to identify in which case validation improvement is needed. In contrast, other Facebook researchers can use this guide to determine whether a particular scale fits the aim of the research design they are planning in their future studies regarding validity and reliability.

Accordingly, the purposes of this study are:

- (a) reviewing the tools used so far to measure Facebook activity about personality traits;
- (b) comparing the characteristics of the instruments;
- (c) verifying the actual reliability and validity of the instruments used;

METHODS

A computerized literature search of words such as "Facebook" AND "Personality" or "Facebook" AND "Questionnaire" [All Fields] or "Facebook" AND "Scale" [All Fields] " has been conducted without including other terms that could bias the search. The research included the most comprehensive coverage of psychological, psychiatric, and educational journals available for literature searches, such as Psyc-INFO, Web of Science, PubMed, and Google Scholar. The search also covered biomedical literature from MEDLINE, life science journals, conference papers, contributions, and doctoral theses.

The research limited itself to (a) articles published in English between 2004, when Facebook was launched, and 2024 and identified as empirical studies; (b) researches conducted on a non-clinical sample (i.e., university students); (c) measuring Facebook psychological attitudes; (d) studies addressing topics relevant the assessment of personality traits. Studies on psychopathological traits such as addiction, alcohol and drug use, body image, as well as the pre-psychotic state were excluded.

The literature review began in 2022 and was completed in the first half of 2024. Overall, the search was limited to articles describing results from studies conducted on the general population and published in peer-reviewed journals. After removing duplicates, the results obtained were sorted by relevance, and the most significant works related to Facebook measurements and personality trait correlations were included. This part's search strategy followed the PRISMA guidelines (see Figure 1) [13].

The articles selected for the review were initially collected by three independent researchers who conducted a thorough literature search. The collected data were then cross-checked to verify the appropriateness of study inclusion. Only those studies that met the inclusion criteria agreed upon by all three researchers were included in the Excel evaluation grid and subsequently assessed independently. A systematic review grid (JBI's critical appraisal tool) was used to enhance the rigor and consistency of the analysis [14]. This grid included criteria such as the methodological quality of the studies, the relevance of the results to the research objectives, the internal and external validity of the studies, and the adequacy of the statistical analyses used. Each study was evaluated against these criteria, allowing for a transparent and structured comparison of the results.

Figure 1. Prisma Flow Chart Diagram for study inclusion

RESULTS

Based on these criteria, the search yielded 43 abstracts that did not always provide information about the established inclusion criteria. Hence, at the first stage of the search, we screened out and excluded the studies that used apps or computerized profile analysis to measure activity on Facebook, which bypassed individual administration. In such cases, the remaining articles were included and reviewed in the next stage of the study. Upon screening the 43 abstracts from the original search, 34 either met the inclusion mentioned above criteria or could not be excluded based on the abstract content. Though these substantive articles are not included in the formal review, we also surveyed them for additional validity evidence.

Following the second stage in the screening process, 24 articles were relevant and potentially eligible for coding. All studies included in the review were based on a cross-sectional design [9,15-36]. Table 1 shows the methodological characteristics of the studies, including nationality (language), sample features, instrument description, personality measures, and associated validity and reliability analysis. Additionally, Table 1 provides a detailed assessment of the quality of the studies using the JBI

Checklist, with quality scores ranging from 7/11 to 10/11. As can be seen from the table, while many studies performed well in terms of methodological rigor, only a subset achieved the highest scores on the quality assessment. This highlights the variability in the robustness of the studies included in the review and underscores the need for more consistent validation approaches across research in this area.

Table 1. Review of Facebook questionnaires and related analysis.

Authors	Country	Instrument	Sample	Instrument characteristics	Personality measures	Validity Analysis	Quality JBI Checklist
Ross et al. (2009) [15]	Canada	Facebook questionnaire	97 undergraduate students (15 men) average age = 21.69 ± 5.40	28-item grouped in 3 categories: basic use, attitudes	NEO Personality Inventory-Revised (NEO-PI-R)	Exploratory factor Analysis	10/11
Orr et al., (2009) [9]	Canada	Attitudes toward Facebook.	103 undergraduate students 16 men and 87 women, mean age 21.50 years (SD 5.29).	Six items from Ellison et al. (2007) and an additional item composed by the authors	Shyness trait - Revised Cheek and Buss Shyness Scale (RCBS-20)	Cronbach's alpha	8/11
Murphy (2010) [16]	Oregon USA	Questionnaire of Facebook use	428 online surveys with a range of 20 to 60 years of age	18-item questionnaire on basic Facebook use	Social Anxiety - Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale (LSAS)	None	7/11
Gosling et al. (2011) [17]	Texas and Missouri USA	Self-Reported Facebook-Related Behaviors	159 psychology student	11-item self-report measure	Ten Item Personality Inventory (TIPI)	None	7/11
Ryan & Xenos (2011) [18]	Australia	Facebook usage questionnaire	1635 self-selected Australian Internet users between 18 and 44 years old	18 questions relating to Facebook usage was adapted from the Facebook Questionnaire by Ross et al. (2009)	NPI; Big Five; Cheek and Buss Shyness Scale (RCBS); Social and Emotional Loneliness Scale; - SELSA-S	None	7/11
Kuo et al. (2011) [19]	Taiwan	Facebook questionnaire	- - -	Facebook Questionnaire shortened by Ryan & Xenos (2011)	TIPI (Ten-Item Personality Inventory)	None	7/11
Ong (2012) [20]	California USA	Facebook questionnaire extended	272 participants, from 18 to 48 years (M = 21.23 years)	Facebook Questionnaire by Ross et al. (2009) with additional items..	Big Five Inventory	Cronbach's alpha	8/11

French (2012) [21]	Ohio USA	Facebook questionnaire	73 participants (36 female and 41 male; M age = 20.25)	12 possible reasons for using Facebook; concern with how they are perceived on Facebook.	Self-Worth Scale	None	7/11
Seto (2012) [22]	Texas USA	Facebook Activity questionnaire	175 participants (147 women, 28 men, Mage = 19.2 years, age range: 18-26 years)	Facebook usage, the motives for using Facebook, and one's emotional connection to Facebook.	Narcissism Personality Inventory; Rosenberg's Self-Esteem Scale; Balanced Inventory of Desirable Responding	Factor Analysis	10/11
Moore & McElroy (2012) [23]	Iowa USA	Survey of Facebook users	219 undergraduate students	Measure of time spent on Facebook, frequency of use, and regret.	Personality International Personality Item Pool (IPIP)	- None	7/11
Tosun (2012) [24]	Turkey	Motives and uses of Facebook	143 Facebook users, 37 males (mean age = 22.63 years; SD = 3.63; range 17-42 years old)	Participants were asked to rate, using a 7-point Likert scale, 46 uses and gratifications.	"True self on the Net" questionnaire	Previous exploratory factor analysis	9/11
Ljepava et al. (2013) [25]	Canada	Facebook Peer Usage Questionnaire	269 undergraduate students	12 statements exploring Facebook use in a participant's offline social networks and peer pressure.	Intimate Friendship Scale; Self Disclosure Scale; Narcissism Personality Inventory (NPI); Hypersensitive Narcissism Scale (HSNS); Trust inventory	Cronbach's alpha	8/11
Lee et al. (2013) [26]	Republic of Korea	Facebook questionnaire	236 college students, 108 male (45.8%) and 128 female (54.2%), 20.6 years old (SD = 2.03)	The online survey questionnaire measured the big five, and narcissism.	The big five (mini-IPIP scales), narcissism (NARQ)	None	7/11
Mims et al. (2013) [27]	Orlando, USA	Facebook usage questions	Participants (n =124; 54% female)	19 Facebook usage questions and two questions concerning profile features.	Liking People Scale	None	7/11

Suresh (2013) [28]	India	Facebook questionnaire	97 people 45% of the respondents were men and 55% were women.	A 28-item with three categories: basic use of Facebook, attitudes and online sociability functions.	Ten Item Personality Inventory (TIPI)	None	7/11
Hong et al., (2014) [29]	Taiwan (Chinese)	Facebook usage scale, and Facebook addiction scale (FAS)	215 university students ; the age group is 18 and 22	Modified Young's Internet addiction scale to Facebook usage	Self-esteem scale by Rosenberg and Lai's personality test	Factor analysis	9/11
Michikyan et al. (2014) [30]	California USA	Self-Presentation-on-Facebook-Questionnaire	Young adults [N = 261, (66 males, 195 females); M = 21.92, SD = 2.76]	17 items that assess online self-presentation grouped in 5 factors: (1) real self; (2) ideal self; (3) false self deception; (4) false self-exploration; (5) false self impress/compare	Ten-Item Personality Inventory (TIPI)	Factor analysis	9/11
McCord et al. (2014) [31]	Missouri USA	Facebook questionnaire (FBQ)	216 Facebook users, 185 women and 31 men, average age was 32.2 years (SD = 12.43), ranging from 18 to 69 years.	10-item measuring frequency of use of socially interactive features of Facebook	Social Interaction Anxiety Scale and social phobia scale-12 (SIASSPS-12).	Cronbach's alpha	8/11
McCord et al. (2014) [31]	Missouri USA	Facebook-Social Interaction Anxiety Scale	216 Facebook users, 185 women and 31 men, average age was 32.2 years (SD = 12.43), ranging from 18 to 69 years.	A seven-item scale designed to measure anxiety and social anxiety symptoms experienced while using the social interaction of Facebook.	Social Interaction Anxiety Scale and social phobia scale-12 (SIASSPS-12).	Cronbach's alpha	8/11
Alloway et al. (2014) [32]	Florida USA	Facebook questionnaire	410 volunteers, ranging between 18 and 50 years	It includes playing games, sharing links, sending private messages, and posting, viewing, or commenting on photos or videos	Interpersonal Reactivity Index (IRI); Narcissistic Personality Inventory-16	Factor Analysis	9/11

Köseoğlu (2015) [33]	Istanbul, Turkey (Turkish and English)	Facebook Belonging Facebook Self- presentation	202 undergraduate university students between 18 to 20	(Information-seeking; Communication; Acceptance-seeking; Connection/caring) (General disclosure; Emotional disclosure; Attention seeking; Actual self- presentation; Hidden self presentation; Ideal self-presentation)	Personality - (NEO- FFI)	None	7/11
Asgar (2015) [34]	Saudi Arabia	Information Seeking in Facebook Scale (ISFS)	Facebook users (N = 150)	23-item scale which resulted in a refined 21-item scale	General Social Media Usage, Online Friendships, Facebook Friendships, and Social Media Use Integration	Exploratory Factor Analysis and Confirmatory Factor Analysis	10/11
Bodroža & Jovanović (2016) [35]	Serbia	Psycho-Social Aspects of Facebook Use	Two samples: 804 FB users ranging from 15 to 62 years (M=26.95 years, SD = 6.35) and 359 students, from 18 to 44 years (M=21.29, SD= 2.96)	The Psycho-Social Aspects of Facebook Use consists of 72 items with a 5-point Likert scale	Big Five Inventory, Brief Sensation Seeking Scale and Fear of Negative Evaluation	Exploratory factor analysis	10/11
Ferenczi et al.(2017) [36]	USA	Uses of Facebook Scale	573 online participants	The prosocial motives scale (13 items); The antisocial motives scale (7 items).		Correlation Analysis, Factor Analysis	9/11

As can be seen, only 14 of the 24 studies can be considered systematically validated, as they report a complete examination of the validation methodology reflected by the quality assessment score. By “systematically validate,” we mean any article whose primary aim is to evaluate several psychometric properties of a scale, including exploratory or confirmatory factorial analysis and the reliability analysis of the scale - Cronbach's alpha. Some articles differ from the selected ones since scale validation is only a secondary aim and provides only partial evidence of the psychometric properties of the scale (for example, studies in which only the reliability is assessed).

A study by Akbağ, Aydoğdu, and Rizzo [47] suggests that phubbing, the act of ignoring someone in favor of a smartphone, has garnered significant research attention recently. When this behavior occurs in parent-child interactions, it is called parental phubbing. A dedicated parental phubbing scale is essential to facilitate comprehensive empirical studies on this phenomenon. This study aimed to develop a reliable tool for assessing perceived parental phubbing and to evaluate its psychometric properties.

Initially, a draft scale with 13 items was formulated based on a literature review and essays by 70 middle school students. With parental consent, the scale's construct validity was tested through exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) on two groups of adolescents aged 10 to 15 (N EFA = 325, N CFA = 210). The EFA identified a 10-item structure with two factors—"interaction interruptions" and "emotional reactions"—explaining 58.81% and 65.02% of the variance for the mother (PPS-M) and father (PPS-F) forms, respectively. The CFA confirmed this structure, showing a good fit for both forms.

Criterion validity was assessed by correlating the scale with the Smartphone Addiction Scale and the UCLA Loneliness Scale-Short Form, revealing significant relationships. Reliability was demonstrated through Cronbach's alpha and McDonald's omega coefficients, exceeding .70 for total and subdimensions. Test-retest reliability coefficients ranged from 0.70 to 0.82 for the PPS-M and 0.70 to 0.81 for the PPS-F, ensuring consistency. In summary, the PPS-M and PPS-F are validated and reliable tools for measuring adolescents' perceptions of their parents' phubbing behavior.

A study by Rizzo and colleagues [48] aimed to assess the psychometric properties and validity of Italian-language instruments that measure Facebook users' motivations based on Joinson's tool. Following the International Test Commission (ITC) guidelines for cross-cultural translation and adaptation, the results indicated that the instrument is reliable and effectively captures age-related differences.

The study demonstrates that younger male users predominantly seek gratification through content sharing and social investigation, while their female counterparts tend to use Facebook for sharing photos and content, indicating a tendency towards self-exhibition. On the other hand, males primarily use social networking sites (SNS) for social investigation, often associated with flirting purposes [49].

The instrument demonstrated sufficient validity and reliability, endorsing its suitability for the target population and providing valuable insights for future research. Nonetheless, the study identified several limitations: (a) the need for clearer item formulations, particularly concerning perceptions of privacy risks; (b) consideration of eliminating the Share Identity scale due to weak correlations; and (c) enhancing sample homogeneity, particularly in terms of age. Moreover, expanding the study to other geographical regions and incorporating demographic variables influencing SNS usage and privacy attitudes could enhance its applicability.

SNS gratification is prevalent across various demographic groups, and despite some constraints, the study offers a promising tool for further investigation into these dynamics.

The major concerns about validity that we identified suggest that researchers should exercise considerable caution when selecting a scale for use in their studies. Only five scales in our review emerged without major validity concerns. However, the cited questionnaires might not be universally suitable for all research purposes, as they can vary significantly in their item formulations, response types, or potential cultural adaptation issues. Hence, researchers interested in the psychological aspects of Facebook use may utilize this review as a preliminary screening tool to choose the most appropriate scale that best addresses their specific hypotheses.

Furthermore, we discovered unresolved validity concerns even among these seemingly robust Facebook scales, implying that researchers should prioritize enhancing the psychometric properties of these measurements before employing them for data collection. These limitations also indicate a significant opportunity for validation studies to refine how Facebook scales

and questionnaires are assessed and utilized for research purposes. Addressing these gaps could significantly improve the reliability and accuracy of future research findings.

Another important consideration for future research is the limited knowledge about the validity of these instruments when administered online. Our literature analysis on SNS, focusing on Facebook activities and psychological aspects such as user motivations, underscored the measurement challenges and the crucial role of the validation process. As well-established in psychometrics, reliable assessment results produce consistent outcomes across repeated or equivalent evaluations [50,51].

Review's limitations

Some limitations of the study need to be emphasized. First of all, it is possible that the literature research, by its very nature, has been able to conceal all the so-called "grey literature," which does not guarantee open access but does not guarantee peer review. Secondly we focused mostly on the questionnaires that included psychological aspects, but the result is also a certain heterogeneity of the instruments. For example, from social anxiety to self-esteem, they investigate very different constructs. That's why we recommend that researchers who want to investigate psychological aspects related to using Facebook learn more about the single tool. We also included studies that did not have the validation of the instrument as their main purpose, posing a problem that the authors declined. However, this does not mean that the instrument is not potentially valid; studies are needed to affirm its validity. Finally, another limitation is that no possible cultural adaptations have been included.

So, this screening is valid only for English-speaking researchers. This partly prevents the results from being generalized to the entire population of researchers. Specific research on translations and linguistic and cultural adaptations would be necessary to overcome this limitation. Otherwise, a possible administration in another language would also require linguistic and cultural adaptation.

CONCLUSION

The present study aimed to review instruments measuring basic Facebook use and psychological and personality aspects, such as the relationship between Facebook use and network characteristics [41]. It also examined the influence of Facebook profiles on job seekers' impressions [52] and concerning dependence [53]. Additionally, some studies explored the relationship between Facebook addiction and various outcomes, including performance, behavior, and mental health [37,45-47,54-61].

These findings suggest that aspects linked to self-image, social relationships, and affective experiences are often neglected compared to more neutral data, such as time spent online and the number of friends. Furthermore, data on the psychometric properties of these questionnaires remain scarce, highlighting the need for further application and adaptation in evidence-based research studies.

Overall, this review underscores the importance of ongoing efforts to enhance the validity and reliability of Facebook-related scales and questionnaires [45]. By improving these tools, researchers can better understand the multifaceted impacts of Facebook use on individuals' psychological and social well-being, ultimately contributing to more nuanced and comprehensive insights in social media research.

This review can be utilized as a comprehensive "psychometric screening" of the scales developed to measure Facebook uses and gratifications from a psychological perspective. Given the recent flourishing expansion of research focusing on social networking as an essential part of people's lives, measuring Facebook use is a critical research area requiring further development.

The importance of accurately measuring Facebook use cannot be overstated, as it provides valuable insights into how individuals interact with social media and the psychological implications of these interactions. Despite several promising scales, many still require additional validation work to ensure their reliability and validity across different populations and contexts.

One significant aspect of this review is its potential to serve as an effective guide for researchers planning to conduct studies on Facebook psychology. By offering a detailed evaluation of existing scales, this review can help researchers save valuable time

and resources that would otherwise be spent on preliminary assessments. It highlights which scales have shown solid psychometric properties and which ones need further refinement, thereby streamlining the selection process for researchers.

Moreover, this review may offer new directions for future studies on the psychometric properties of Facebook scales. It underscores the need for continuous validation efforts and encourages researchers to develop and test new scales that can better capture the multifaceted nature of Facebook use. For instance, future research could explore the cultural adaptability of these scales, ensuring they are relevant and accurate across diverse cultural contexts. Additionally, studies could focus on refining the items within existing scales to enhance their sensitivity and specificity in measuring various psychological constructs related to Facebook use. Another crucial area for future research highlighted by this review is the need to examine the longitudinal stability of these scales. Understanding how individuals' Facebook use and related psychological outcomes evolve can provide deeper insights into the long-term effects of social media engagement. Furthermore, integrating these scales with other psychological assessments could offer a more holistic view of how Facebook interacts with various aspects of mental health, personality, and social behavior.

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